

Deciphering signals of landscape disturbance in an erosive cohesive-bank creek (late middle ages, southern Spain): The sedimentary sink role of knickpoints

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ABSTRACT

The Yeguas Creek (Guadalquivir Valley, southern Iberian Peninsula) is a dominantly erosive, cohesive-bank creek submitted to bank destabilization, deep channel incision, and several contemporaneous knickpoints along the river profile, where recorded 20 to 200 m³/s floods (1945 to the present) generate hydraulic jumps. Two fill (aggradational) terraces were identified and analyzed: (1) Terrace 1 (T1), topping an aggradational sequence of cohesive soils to a fluvio-lacustrine tufa system (Roman Period, Morphosedimentary Unit 1: MU-1); and (2) a confined Terrace 2 (T2), topping Late Medieval (1200–1400 CE) to modern (1960s) river flood deposits (Morphosedimentary Unit 2: MU-2).

The Late Medieval deposits (MU-2) constitute a solitary pulse of river aggradation preserved in this dominantly erosive setting over the last two millennia (after Roman Period). Unlike the standard horizontal bedding of aggradational fluvial terraces, the Late Medieval terrace in the Yeguas River exhibits a downstream-dipping, concave-up scour base infilled by poorly sorted and massive deposits. These contain high variability in grain size (gravels, sands, and silts) and grain type (cm-scale charcoal, freshwater fossils, and pottery remains). Sedimentary features, internal structure and the recent hydrogeomorphologic behavior of the Yeguas Creek, allow us to interpret the Late Medieval terrace as an ancient aggradational knickpoint. This cut-and-fill structure (knickpoint) is controlled by the high sediment discharge transported by the stream during Late Middle Age floods. This Late Medieval sediment legacy captured in the aggradational knickpoint of the Yeguas Creek—alongside other reported Late Middle Ages river terraces in the Guadalquivir Valley—is discussed in the context of the river's adjustment over 250 years of military activities impacting a frontier land (between the Christian Kingdom of Castile and the Muslim Nasrid Kingdom of Granada). Human activities in the Late Middle Ages may have accelerated landscape and river degradation in the southern Iberian Peninsula, which began after the Roman Period.

1. Introduction

Stream geometry adjusts to discharge regimes and sediment loads; consequently, changes in discharge/sediment load ratios result in alterations to geometric variables and the lateral and vertical distribution of fluvial facies (Blum and Törnquist, 2000). Geomorphic instability reflecting non-equilibrium landscape scenarios can be recorded by contemporaneous erosional processes (e.g., upstream channel incision or river degradation) and alluvial processes (e.g., downstream flood-plain aggradation) (Belmont, 2011). The activity of rivers and their

response to external forcing (climate, tectonics, and land-use changes) are the main controls on landscape incision (Wobus et al., 2010; Baynes et al., 2018). The geometry of a river's longitudinal profile is controlled by time-invariant factors (e.g., substrate lithology) and variable factors such as base level, sediment supply, and river discharge (Wobus et al., 2006; Jansen et al., 2011; Lague, 2014). Channel incision and lateral widening processes characterize dis-equilibrated fluvial systems. Both features can be linked to climate change and anthropogenic actions when they drive excess sediment-transporting capacity (Simon and Rinaldi, 2006). Landscapes responding to long-term shifts in climate and

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river incision rates may adjust through changes in the extent of cohesive substrate over relatively short timescales (Sklar and Dietrich, 2001). Transformation of cut-and-fill landscapes dominated by incision in highly variable discharge stream channels commonly reflects the variable character, rate, and extent of human landscape modification in semiarid, poorly resilient settings (Brierley and Fryirs, 1999; Simon and Rinaldi, 2006). However, the magnitude of physical landscape alteration and environmental disruption provoked by land-use changes is complex to quantify (Marsh and Kealhofer, 2014).

Geological conditions or processes that modify erosion rates are commonly reflected in steep erosive reaches along stream longitudinal profiles, known as ‘knickpoints’ (Brush and Wolman, 1960). These convex-up reaches along the naturally concave, equilibrium longitudinal river profile are interpreted as evidence that the river is adjusting to re-establish an equilibrium profile (Gardner, 1983). These erosive instabilities propagate upstream via knickpoint retreat to achieve system balance following a change in boundary conditions (Bishop et al., 2005). The evolution of knickpoints and their retreat or upstream migration along longitudinal river profiles have been analyzed as signals of river adjustment reflecting climatic (as a topographic proxy) and tectonic perturbations (Schwanghart and Scherler, 2020). Thus, knickpoint analysis is key to understanding catchment responses to perturbations, landscape recovery times, and sediment flux from the catchment (Bishop et al., 2005).

The Mediterranean landscape is among the most heavily human-disturbed regions, exhibiting increasing land degradation over time (Hooke, 2006; Casana, 2008; García-Ruiz, 2010). Various paleoclimatic proxies from the Western Mediterranean region indicate a progressive aridification over the last 5000 years (Camuera et al., 2023), punctuated by abrupt climate events. Palynological studies report that Late Holocene vegetation degradation in Southern Spain since the Argaric period (4300–3600 cal years BP) was driven mainly by long-term global climatic forcing (a persistent positive mode of the North Atlantic Oscillation/NAO) combined with short-term local-to-regional human impact (Carrión et al., 2001; Schulte, 2002; Butzer, 2005; Carrión et al., 2010; Jiménez-Moreno et al., 2013; Ramos-Román et al., 2016; Gázquez et al., 2025). Intense deforestation in Southern Spain over the last five millennia was exacerbated by anthropogenic disturbances, including agriculture, mining, and pastoralism (Carrión et al., 2001, 2010; García-Ruiz, 2010; García-Alix et al., 2013). Under an overall arid context, human landscape disturbances may have triggered soil erosion and alluvial aggradation.

The landscape of the Southern Iberian Peninsula in the Western Mediterranean, with its Late Holocene history of climate change (aridification) and human modification, represents a highly sensitive setting for reconstructing the effects of climate and land-use changes on river processes. Abundant climatic and human impact proxies (e.g., pollen, geochemistry) reported from external river settings in the area (i.e., lacustrine deposits, speleothems, tree rings) over the last 20 years allow us to contrast and discuss the river adjustments identified here with well-constrained data from other, more continuous sedimentary records in the region (see references above and along the text).

This paper presents a comprehensive reconstruction of the hydrogeomorphic evolution of Yeguas Creek, beginning with a characterization of the study area's geological context and current channel morphology within the Guadalquivir River Valley. Following an outline of the stratigraphic, sedimentological, and geochronological methodologies employed, the results section details both recent hydrological channel adjustments and the long-term sedimentary record preserved in fluvial terraces. These findings facilitate a chronological interpretation of the river's dynamics over the last two millennia, tracing the transition from Roman-era aggradation to incisional dominance. The study concludes with a discussion evaluating the driving forces behind these geomorphic shifts, specifically weighing the influence of climatic oscillations against anthropogenic impacts—most notably, the landscape disturbances caused by medieval frontier warfare.

2. Geomorphological characteristics of the studied stretch of the Yeguas Creek

The Guadalquivir River is the primary watercourse in the southern Iberian Peninsula, flowing from a region influenced by the Eastern Mediterranean climate to the Western Atlantic realm. The regional map in Fig. 1a shows the major rivers (light blue lines) and basins (dark gray lines) bordering the Guadalquivir Basin. Also, the main systems of mountain ranges (i.e., the Sierra Morena and the Baetic System) constraining the Guadalquivir river course are marked with dashed-dotted lines. This study focuses on a small tributary (Yeguas Creek) of the main tributary (Genil River) in the Guadalquivir River Valley. The Yeguas Creek basin (highlighted in red) covers more than 300 km².

The study area is located at the boundary of two central geological and geomorphological units: a mountainous landscape represented by the fold-and-thrust belt of the External Zones (Subbetic Subzone) of the Betic Cordillera orogen to the south, and a basin landscape defined by the Miocene Foreland Guadalquivir Basin to the north (Fig. 1b). The Yeguas Creek headwaters are situated in the Subbetic rocks represented by tectonically deformed Keuper Triassic rocks (red sandstones, lutites, gypsum, and halites) and the Jurassic-Cretaceous Carbonated (limestones and marls) Massifs of the Sierra de los Caballos and Sierra de Estepa reliefs (Fig. 1b). The creek then flows northwards composed of, sub-horizontal, well-stratified marine Miocene sandstones and marls, and alluvial Quaternary deposits (dominantly conglomerates, sands, and muds) from alluvial fans, glacia, playa-lakes and river terraces (see Jiménez-Bonilla et al., 2023, for more regional tectonic details).

Yeguas Creek is a 25 km-long, ephemeral creek that flows south to north. The Yeguas River catchment is located in the north of a Quaternary closed (endorheic) and semi-closed upland plain (Antequera Plain), situated on the Mediterranean-Atlantic water divide. The Antequera Plain shows Quaternary-to-recent active or dissected internal drainage with ephemeral lacustrine areas characterized by low water levels (playa lakes) (Rodríguez-Rodríguez, 2007). Yeguas Creek is a narrow, steep-gradient stream dissecting a plain landscape ranging from 450 to 170 m a.s.l. (Fig. 2a). Along Yeguas Creek, there are two contrasting sectors with different slopes, separated by an erosional knickpoint currently located in Casariche: (1) a 14 km-long, gently sloping stretch upstream of Casariche, and (2) an 11 km-long, narrow (20–75 m wide), steep (9% slope) and deeply incised (10–15 m deep) lower stretch downstream of Casariche (Fig. 2b–c). Along the 11 km-long lower stretch of Yeguas Creek downstream of Casariche, the incised channel exhibits a sequence of four stepped knickpoints denoted by KP1 to KP4 in Fig. 3a. The incised channel shows stretches with a tightly sinuous trajectory and other narrower and straightened stretches (Fig. 3b–f).

3. Methods

A detailed stratigraphic, sedimentological, and geochronological framework was established for the Yeguas Creek terraces sequence. The fluvial landscape evolution and human interaction in the study area over the last two millennia were reconstructed using terrace morphostratigraphy and mapping, both transverse and longitudinal river valley profiles, facies analysis of river deposits, radiocarbon dating, and the archaeological characterization of pottery and settlements.

Three levels containing organic remains—two with charcoal (located at the base of morphosedimentary unit 2) and one with plant leaves (located at the top of the same unit)—were sampled for radiocarbon dating. Two samples were dated from each of these levels to accurately constrain their chronology. The six samples were cleaned mechanically and with Milli-Q water. Radiocarbon analyses were performed at the Poznan Radiocarbon Laboratory (Poland) and the Centro Nacional de Aceleradores (Seville, Spain). The ¹⁴C ages were calibrated using OxCal 4.4 software (Bronk Ramsey, 2021) along with the IntCal20 (Reimer et al., 2020) and Bomb21NH2 (Hua et al., 2022) calibration curves. Calibrated ages are expressed in calendar years AD.

In addition, we applied standard tools to characterize the fluvial geomorphology of Yeguas Creek (Kondolf and Piégay, 2003) and to correlate it with the catchment hydrology (Brutsaert, 2005) since 1950. We combined topographic analysis based on LiDAR data and ortho-photogrammetry, two-dimensional numerical simulation of hydraulic processes with Iber+ using Graphics Processing Unit (García-Feal et al., 2018), frequency analysis of the precipitation series AEMETv2 (Peral-García et al., 2017), and streamflow data using PeakFQ (Veilleux et al., 2014). The selected data and the software are freely available at <https://www.ign.es>, <https://www.chguadalquivir.es>, and <https://www.iberaula.es> (accessed on 1 July 2025). The methods are described in greater detail in earlier publications (Bohorquez and Del Moral-Erencia, 2017; Bohorquez et al., 2023). The main novelty with respect to our previous works is the steep slope of Yeguas Creek, which induces hydraulic regimes that transition from supercritical to subcritical flow through a cascade of hydraulic jumps, potentially associated with the formation of knickpoints and terraces.

Joint analysis of DEM data (including knickpoints, channel gradient, longitudinal profiles, and planform) together with quantitative modeling of hydraulic variables enables a better understanding of sedimentary and geomorphic processes (Baker et al., 2022). The four knickpoints (KP1-KP4) distributed along the thalweg profile, shown in Fig. 3a, define four river stretches with increasing downstream slopes of 0.63%, 0.66%, 0.71%, and 0.87%. Such steep slopes drive high flow velocities and lead to incision over time, independent of water discharge. Transitions between river stretches with different slopes occur at sharp bends and at sudden contractions or expansions of channel width (see the plan views in Fig. 3d–f for knickpoints 2, 3, and 4). There, local hydraulic jumps also develop (denoted as HJ 3, 7, and 8). Furthermore, numerous hydraulic jumps occur along the Yeguas River (from km 1 to 11), causing sudden transitions between supercritical and subcritical flow and steep gradients in flow depth and velocity. In particular, HJ 4 and 5 could be associated with the formation of the studied terraces, which are located between them, similar to submarine channels (Guiastrenec-Faugas et al., 2020).

4. Results

4.1. Recent hydrogeomorphic behavior of the Yeguas Creek

Historical floods with water discharges from 20 to 200 m³/s display high variability in flow velocities along the cohesive-bank confined channel (Fig. 3c–g). High flood flow velocities (above 8 m/s) are widely found in straightened and narrow stretches upstream of more sinuous and wider stretches, where the flood flow velocity sharply decreases, forming hydraulic jumps independently of the peak water discharge (see HJ1 to HJ8 in Fig. 3a). For instance, a flash flood occurred on the 21st October 2018 in the Yeguas Creek, which provoked the migration of the main channel about 10 m along the cross-stream direction in section AA' of Fig. 3 g in less than 12 h. The streambank suffered mass failure and resulted in channel widening, as shown in Fig. 4a. Similarly, the flood destabilized the left channel bank of the cross-section BB' further upstream and led to channel widening by mass-wasting processes, resulting in higher and steeper streambank (Fig. 4b). Such a large magnitude flood occurrence was natural as it developed from an intense rainfall shorter than 12 h with an accumulated precipitation larger than 100 mm (Fig. 4c) and a peak precipitation intensity of 13.6 mm/h (Fig. 4d). Such a rainfall event represents the largest one recorded since 1950 (i.e., the year that systematic measures in Spain began).

Sediment derived from streambank failures can be interpreted, in the current case, as one of the primary sources of sediment in the incised channel of Yeguas Creek, as is the case in other watersheds (Simon and Darby, 1997). In 2018, unstable banks supplied enormous quantities of sediment to the flow, which we have quantified relative to the post-flood wetted area for the water discharge of 100 m³/s (and 200 m³/s) estimated in the gauge station (and paleo-indicators), recall Fig. 4d. The

Fig. 1. a. Basins of the main rivers in southern Spain, showing the Yeguas Creek subbasin (perimeter in red line) in the south-central part of the Guadalquivir River Basin, b. Geological map of the Yeguas Creek subbasin. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

eroded sediments (red area in Figs. 4a–b) amounted to 52.5% (28.8%) and 108.6% (63.3%) in sections AA' (Fig. 4a) and BB' (Fig. 4b), respectively, whilst the aggradation area was 27.8% (15.3%) and 63.4% (37.1%). The channel adjustment can also be interpreted as a mechanism for dissipating energy and reducing flow velocity and stream power, owing to the larger wetted perimeter of the post-flood cross-section.

Channel incision has developed since the 1950s; however, it has been triggered by long-rain floods, with durations longer than one week and higher recurrence than in 2018. More than 90% of the hydrologic years exhibited an accumulated precipitation for 24 h (referred to as daily

Fig. 2. a. The map shows the Yeguas Creek subbasin (perimeter in solid black line) into the Guadalquivir River basin in southern Spain -see location in Fig. 1-. Red and white points indicate the two studied river sections along the downstream stretch of the Casariche town river (cyan solid line), as shown in satellite orthoimages (b) and (c). Look at the deep incision of the Yeguas riverbed 10–15 m below the Terrace 1 (T1) and the preservation into the creek of a lower discontinuous and confined terrace (T2). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

rainfall depth from now on) in the range of 16 to 53 mm associated to the recurrence intervals of 1 to 5 years, see Fig. 4c. The characteristic values of the peak streamflow vary typically from 10 to 20 m³/s, as shown, for example, in Fig. 4e for the three months rainfall of December 2009 to February 2010. An exceptional flood occurred in 1969, with a daily rainfall depth of 95.5 mm and an annual precipitation of 738 mm, similar to the 750 mm measured in 2018. The impacts of the inundation on the channel's fluvial morphology can be observed in historical orthophotos dating back to 1956 (Fig. 4g), particularly in Section AA'. The arrows in Fig. 4a indicate the location of the main channel on those days, which formed a terrace when the channel was displaced and incised to its present location. Morphological processes were significantly evident during the period from 1956 (Fig. 4g) to 1977 (Fig. 4h). Subsequently, the channel remained in approximately the same location from 1977 to 2004. Sedimentary activity was reactivated from 2004 to 2013 as a consequence of the long-rain floods that occurred in the Guadalquivir Basin from 2009 to 2013 (Bohorquez and Del Moral-Erencia, 2017). Lastly, an exceptional migration of the main channel occurred during the 2018 flood, displacing it to the opposite side of its 1956 location, as observed in recent 2022 orthophotography (Fig. 4i).

4.2. Yeguas River terraces, deposits, and chronology

Two fill terraces are identified along the longitudinal profile of Yeguas Creek: a higher, laterally extensive terrace 10–15 m above the modern riverbed (Terrace 1 or T1), and a lower, discontinuous terrace confined within the cohesive banks of the creek 5 m above the riverbed (Terrace 2 or T2) (Figs. 5 and 6). Both are aggradational terraces overlying deposits grouped into two morphosedimentary units: (1)

Morphosedimentary Unit 1 (MU-1), topped by Terrace 1 (T1), and (2) Morphosedimentary Unit 2 (MU-2), topped by Terrace 2 (T2) (Figs. 5 and 6).

4.2.1. Morphosedimentary unit 1 (MU-1) – Late Holocene (?) to Roman period

Terrace T1 is an extensive terrace located at 250 m a.s.l. and 10–15 m above the modern riverbed (Fig. 5a). T1 is the top surface of the Morphosedimentary Unit 1 (MU-1). MU-1 overlies the pre-Quaternary basement rocks (Miocene sandstones and marls). In terms of lithofacies, two sub-units have been distinguished within MU-1 from bottom to top:

1. Sub-unit MU-1a (lower MU-1): Composed of >10 m of cohesive, fine-grained, dominantly horizontally bedded paleosol horizons (Fig. 5b).
2. Sub-unit MU-1b (upper MU-1): Represented by 2–3 m of dark, fine-grained deposits with carbonate nodules and gravel channels composed of limestone clasts and phytoclasts coated by laminated microbial encrustations (oncoids) (Figs. 5c–e). Roman tegulae have been found within these deposits.

4.2.2. Morphosedimentary unit 2 (MU-2) - late medieval (1200–1400 CE) to 1960s

MU-2 consists of 3 m thick, sharp-based erosional deposits capped by Terrace 2 (T2). Terrace T2 lies 5 m below Terrace T1 (Fig. 6a, b) and 5 m above the modern riverbed. Thus, MU-2 deposits appear confined within vertical banks constituted by the cohesive materials of the MU-1 paleosols. The MU-2 outcrops are very discontinuous and are mainly preserved along the river where the channel cross-section widens due to

Fig. 3. a-b. Longitudinal profile and plan view of the Yeguas Creek downstream of Casariche town (cyan solid line in Fig. 2a). Look at the knickpoints location (KP1–4) and the cascade of eight hydraulic jumps (HJ1–8) along the streamflow illustrated for simulated discharges of 20, 100, and 200 m³/s, c-f. Flow velocity distribution for the 200 m³/s streamflow along the scour area downstream of Casariche town and three knickpoints (KP2–4). g. Detail view of the velocity field in the river bends where the river terraces were studied, showing three hydraulic jumps with a discharge of 200 m³/s.

previous bank collapse.

MU-2 consists of 3 m thick, sharp-based, typically graded gravel and sandy deposits (Fig. 6c, d). It is divided into two parts:

1. MU-2a: A 2.5 m thick lower part consisting of sharp-based, typically graded gravels and sands containing abundant charcoal, freshwater bivalves, gastropods, and pottery remnants (Fig. 6e, f). Four radiocarbon dates from two stratified charcoal levels (~50 cm in length) constrained the age of the base of MU-2a to 1200–1400 CE (CAS 07 2σ: 1178–1278 CE and CAS 13 2σ: 1299–1408 CE; Table 1).
2. MU-2b: A 50 cm thick, planar-laminated granule-to-sandy bed at the top of MU-2 containing abundant anthropogenic remnants (e.g.,

bottle caps) (Fig. 6 g), where radiocarbon dating suggests an age around 1965 CE (CAS 24: 1961–1969 CE).

5. Interpretation of the morphosedimentary record: Reconstruction of the Yeguas River evolution over the last two millennia

5.1. Stages of river aggradation, degradation and terracing

The Holocene geomorphic evolution of the Yeguas Creek reveals two well-defined river stages with respect to deposition, erosion, and terracing. The first stage (MU-1a), spanning the Holocene (?) to the

Fig. 4. a-b. Upstream view of the cross-sections AA' and BB' (see location in Fig. 3 g) after the 21st October 2018 flood downcutting, respectively, the right and left streambanks. The arrows in panel 3a depict the location of the thalweg observed in a series of orthophotos. c. The maximum value of the daily rainfall depth each year since 1950. d-e. Hietographs and hydrographs during the wet hydrologic winter 2009–2010 (panel e) and the flash flood that occurred in October 2018 (panel d). f. The annual precipitation since 1950. g-i. Orthophotos showing the migration of the main channel in 1956 (green solid line), 1977 (blue solid line), and 2022 (magenta solid line) that provoked the formation of the terrace in the cross-section AA' (red solid line) depicted in panel a. Also, the dots indicate the location of the thalweg in additional years, as for the arrows in panel a.

Roman Period, was dominantly aggradational. In contrast, the last two millennia of terracing and depositional history in the Yeguas Creek reveal the dominance of erosional processes, river incision, and landscape degradation from the end of the Roman Period to the present day (Fig. 7).

5.1.1. A fluvio-lacustrine plain topping the Holocene pre-Roman plateau

A shift in fluvial style occurred during the Roman Period when the pre-Roman aggradational floodplain landscape with well-developed

soils (MU-1a) was substituted by a braided fluvial-to-lacustrine tufa system (MU-1b), fed by water springs from the nearby carbonate massifs (Sierra de los Caballos and Sierra de Estepa) (Fig. 7a). A paleolake from the Roman Period has been reported based on the study of Roman archaeological sites in the Albina depression within the Yeguas River catchment (see location in Fig. 1b) (Jiménez-Bonilla et al., 2023).

5.1.2. Creek incision, river terrace 1 (Roman period to middle ages), and a late medieval aggradational pulse (1200–1400 CE)

After the Roman Period and before the Late Middle Ages, the fluvio-lacustrine plain was strongly dissected, and incision of Yeguas Creek began. The channel headcut incision disconnected the lower course of the channel from its attached floodplain, which became Terrace T1. River incision began at that time and remains active to the present. Over the last two millennia, characterized by landscape degradation and river incision, only one pulse of river deposition occurred within the Yeguas Creek channel between 1200 and 1400 CE (Fig. 7b).

The poorly sorted MU-2a deposits, containing highly heterogeneous components such as lithoclasts, charcoal, pottery, and invertebrate fossil remains (bivalves and gastropods), are explained by two distinct sediment sources: transport by channel flow and runoff erosion from the upper terrace (Terrace T1). This erosion represents the degrading fluvial plain adjacent to the incised channel (Fig. 8). The terrace slope steepens toward the channel cliffs, encouraging overflow currents toward the channel. This overflow acceleration drove soil erosion at the top of the channel banks. Highly concentrated sediment floods in Middle Age

allowed for sediment deposition and the preservation of the downstream, steeply scoured surface infilled by the deposits (Fig. 8). The sigmoidal bedding of the deposits, following the erosional basal surface, indicates that this erosive feature, which truncates the cohesive banks, can be interpreted as a cut-and-fill river structure (i.e., an aggradational knickpoint). Radiocarbon dating points to a time interval between the 12th and 15th centuries CE for the base of this sub-unit (Table 1).

5.1.3. Last flood bed (ca. 1965 CE) and river terrace 2

The sub-unit MU-2b deposits are interpreted as upper-flow-regime deposits that record a river flood. This unit is only found in wider river sections. These channel expansion zones represent favorable settings for river deposition linked to a rapid decrease in flow energy during floods (Benito et al., 2003). Radiocarbon dating (ca. 1965 CE; Table 1) and anthropogenic remnants (e.g., bottle caps) confirmed an Anthropocene age. MU-2b was likely deposited during some of the exceptional floods that occurred in the 1960s (i.e., 1969 river flood, which had a daily rainfall depth of 95.5 mm and an annual precipitation of 738 mm, Fig. 4c).

Fig. 5. a. Fluvial terraces and morphosedimentary units of the Yeguas Creek in river Section 2 (see rectangle in fig. 2c for location): Older terrace (Terrace T1) is a 10 m above the riverbed, laterally extensive terrace. The younger terrace (Terrace T2) is a 5 m above riverbed, discontinuous and bank-confined terrace filling bank-eroded scours into T1 deposits (dashed lines). Morphosedimentary unit 1 (MU-1) represents deposits (mainly palaeosol horizons) underlying the terrace T1, and morphosedimentary unit 2 (MU-2) represents bank-confined and discontinuous deposits underlying the terrace T2. Look at the recent channel confined within vertical banks of cohesive material below T1. b. Erosional vertical riverbank constituted by 10 m thick cohesive palaeosols of the morphosedimentary unit 1 (MU-1) underlying the terrace T1. Look at the dark palaeosol horizon in the middle of the cliff (arrow). c. Panoramic view of river Section 1 (see location in fig. 2b) showing morphosedimentary unit 1b (MU-1b) deposits at the top and remnants of a 15 m above the riverbed, d-e. Channel of gravel-sized oncoids (carbonate-coated clasts) overlying a dark fine-grained bed of the upper part of the morphosedimentary unit 1 (MU-1b) and overlying the MU-1a palaeosols sequence (see location in panoramic view 4c) (hammer to scale). Look at the remains of a watermill used till it was destroyed, and the riverbed deeply incised during the 70's floods.

Fig. 6. a. Fluvial terraces of the Yeguas Creek in river Section 1 (see location in fig. 2c) showing morphosedimentary units: Morphosedimentary Unit 1 (MU-1) represents the deposits capped by the terrace T1, and Morphosedimentary Unit 2 (MU-2) represents the deposits topped by the terrace T2, b. Interpreted cross-section drawn from the previous panoramic picture, c. Stratigraphic log of the Morphosedimentary Unit 2 (MU-2) in the river section showed in fig. 6a-b, d. A view showing the Morphosedimentary Unit 2 (MU-2) which is divided into a lower part (MU-2a) and an upper part (MU-2b) (hammer in central photo to scale), e. A detail of erosion-based (dashed line) gravel channel of the morphosedimentary unit 2 (MU-2), truncating cohesive materials (palaeosoils) of the morphosedimentary unit 1 (MU-1). Gravel filling of the channel contains pottery remnants, f. Charcoals, gastropods, and bivalves (arrows) at the base of the MU-2 (MU-2b), g. Detail of the deposits at the top of MU-2 (see location in Fig. 6d). It is a horizontally-laminated gravelly sandy deposit containing anthropic remains (i.e., bottle cap -arrow-).

The impacts of the inundation on the channel's fluvial morphology can be inferred by comparing recent data with historical orthophotos dating back to 1956, particularly in Section AA'. The arrows in Fig. 4a indicate the location of the main channel at that time, which formed a

terrace when the channel was displaced and incised to its present location. The flood recorded in MU-2b deposits was the last aggradational event in Yeguas Creek. Subsequently, rapid channel incision has proceeded to the present day, terracing the top of MU-2 (Terrace 2)

(Fig. 7c). This incision left nearshore watermills of the 20th century hanging 10 to 15 m above the new riverbed, leading to their abandonment (see dam remains attached to an abandoned watermill in Fig. 5d–e).

6. Factors controlling the evolution of the Yeguas Creek

6.1. The Iberian Roman humid period (IRHP)

The development of a fluvial-lacustrine tufa system during the Roman Period (MU-1b) is consistent with higher piezometric levels during an overall humid and warm period (Iberian Roman Humid Period – IRHP) in southern Iberia from ~650 BCE to 350 CE (Martín-Puertas et al., 2010; Jiménez-Moreno et al., 2013; Gázquez et al., 2023, 2025, among others). This coincided with the Holocene peak of forest degradation in the mountains and highlands of southern Spain, which occurred during the Roman occupation (Carrion et al., 2010). This human pressure in the hills is evidenced in the study area by the first appearance of coarse-grained sediment supply (limestone pebbles) from the surrounding massifs (the Jurassic Carbonate Massifs of Sierra de Estepa). However, the high sediment discharge resulting from the erosion of deforested mountains was offset by high aquifer water discharge. Under a context of overall high precipitation in southern Iberia, springs surrounding the carbonate massifs likely drove the deposition of tufa and travertine carbonates within the fluvial and lacustrine systems of the area.

6.2. The late medieval fluvial sedimentary legacy

In terms of climate, the Medieval Climate Anomaly (MCA: 900–1300 CE) in the Iberian Peninsula was characterized by a warm, dry climate that evolved into colder conditions during the Little Ice Age (LIA: 1300–1850 CE) (Björck et al., 2006; Moreno et al., 2012; Jiménez-Moreno et al., 2015). Two of the 11 sub-decadal-scale arid events (droughts) of the last two millennia identified in the Iberian Peninsula occurred in the Late Middle Ages (1250 CE and 1450) (Camuera et al., 2023). Speleothem and tree-ring records from Morocco and the Iberian Peninsula suggest a variable positive NAO during the MCA (Wassenburg et al., 2013).

The medieval river aggradation preserved in MU-2a of the Yeguas Creek represents a pulse of anomalously high sediment-to-water discharge ratios during the Late Middle Ages. The deposits of the lower part of Morphosedimentary Unit 2 (MU-2a) represent the thickest depositional episode recorded and preserved within the lower, confined course of the creek, downstream of Casariche. The lack of other post-Roman Period deposits in the Yeguas Creek supports the hypothesis that the highest rate of (coarse-grained) sediment supply in the last two millennia occurred during the Late Medieval Period. This Late Medieval alluviation peak in Yeguas Creek was also reported in the main river of the basin (Guadalquivir River) (1160–1440 CE) (Uribelarrea and Benito, 2008).

Channel beds aggrade when sediment supply exceeds maximum bedload transport rates (Blum and Törnquist, 2000). Creeks confined

within cohesive banks (i.e., mudstones or clayey soil horizons, such as those of the Yeguas Creek) can rarely exceed bedload transport rates via bank erosion, as fine-grained material is transported in suspension (see the analysis of the 2018 catastrophic flood event in the Yeguas Creek, Section 4.1., Fig. 4). Therefore, aggradation in these dominantly incisional, cohesive-bank channels can only occur when a high ratio of coarse-grained sediment is supplied to the channel from catchment bedrock or adjacent terrace runoff.

This high sediment availability during the Late Middle Ages has been attributed to land-use changes (e.g., agricultural land expansion and deforestation) and to periodic clusters of extreme precipitation events (Butzer, 2005). However, other studies suggest that the Muslim agrarian society occupying the Iberian Peninsula (Al-Andalus: 711–1492 CE) represented an exception to the long-term history of environmental over-exploitation, utilizing ‘environmentally friendly’ agricultural techniques that did not result in significant soil erosion or clearance (Castro et al., 2000).

In terms of medieval geopolitics, the study area was located just north of the border between the Christian Kingdom of Castile and the Muslim Nasrid Kingdom of Granada for over three centuries (1200–1492 CE), extending from the East (Mediterranean coast) to the West (Atlantic Coast – Gulf of Cádiz) of southern Iberia (Fig. 9). For over two centuries and a half (1200–1450 CE), this frontier was subject to military land use, including scorched-earth tactics, deforestation, abandonment of fields, and extensive grazing. Military activities, such as the systematic felling of trees and human-set fires, exhausted the land, leading to subsequent abandonment (Quesada, 1989; Ladero-Quesada, 2002). These military strategies between the Kingdom of Castile and Al-Andalus were recounted in the verses of the epic anonymous poem *Cantar de Mio Cid* (1207), contemporaneous with the Medieval morphosedimentary unit (MU-2a) in the Yeguas Creek: ‘tierras negras las va parando’ (he is laying waste to the lands) (v. 938) or ‘tajávales las huertas’ (they razed their orchards) (v. 1172) (Anonymous (1207), 2026). Such human activities would result in the formation of charcoal levels within the sediments, such as those dated in the MU-2a in the Yeguas Creek. Landscape disturbance likely accelerated soil erosion through runoff and rill erosion on agricultural land, thereby increasing the rate of sediment supply to rivers during flood events. Other Late Medieval alluvial records from tributary valleys of the Guadalquivir Basin (e.g., Larva Salado Creek; see Fig. 9), which also drain this frontier land, exhibit similar patterns (García-García et al., 2016). The sedimentary facies of these deposits, alternating with ash/charcoal levels, were interpreted as resulting from short-transport sheet flows fed by high concentrations of fine-grained fractions from fire-induced soil runoff episodes (García-García et al., 2016). These have also been described as a singular, isolated alluvial peak over the last two millennia. Anomalously cold summers between 1360–1410 CE (reconstructed from tree-ring records of long-lived *Pinus nigra* in the region) have been attributed to increased surface albedo, likely due to war-related deforestation (Dorado-Liñán et al., 2015). We propose that the 250 years of warfare that impacted the landscape were the primary factor controlling regional physical anomalies, and thus the medieval sedimentary legacy (see this term in Allan James, 2013) preserved in the terraces of the rivers draining that

Table 1

Radiocarbon results for the MU 1 of Yeguas creek calibrated using the IntCal20 (Reimer et al., 2020) and Bomb21NH2 (Hua et al., 2022) calibration curves (Reimer et al., 2020) by means of OxCal 4.4 (Bronk Ramsey, 2021). Poz: Poznan Radiocarbon Laboratory (Poland), CAN Centro Nacional de Aceleradores (Seville, Spain).

Material	Sample	Lab ID (Poznan)	¹⁴ C age (yr BP) or *pMC	±	2σ range (cal yr AD)	Median (cal yr AD)	LAB ID (Seville)	¹⁴ C age (yr BP) or *pMC	±	2σ range (cal yr AD)	Median (cal yr AD)
Charcoal	CAS 13	Poz-189,203	600	30	1301–1408	1347	CNA 7039	615	29	1299–1401	1348
Charcoal	CAS 7	Poz-189,204	810	30	1178–1276	1240	CNA 7038	804	29	1180–1278	1243
Plant remains	CAS 24	Poz-189,202	*170.07	0.38	1961–1969	1965	CNA 7040	*167.98	0.53	1961–1969	1965

Fig. 7. Reconstruction of the last two millennium geomorphic (terracing) and morphosedimentary evolution of the Yeguas Creek downstream Casariche town from longitudinal and transversal river sections: a. Roman Period: A lacustrine-fluvial tufa system occupied the river valley when the fluvial plain was intensively inhabited, b. End of Roman to Late Medieval ages (1200–1400 CE): A dominantly river degradation stage represented by headcutting channel incision and terracing (Terrace T1) was interrupted by a punctual channel aggradation during 1200–1400 CE, c. Early Anthropocene to nowadays: A radiocarbon-aged flood slackwater deposit occurred around 1965 CE debuted a series of river floods in the last 50 years provoking upstream migration of the erosional knickpoint which is located nowadays in the town of Casariche.

Fig. 8. Scheme showing channel aggradation (MU-2) in a sediment sink (i.e., cut-and-fill structure or knickpoint) along the Yeguas Creek during Late Middle Ages (1200–1400 CE) river floods. After the Medieval Period, channel incision into MU-2 has continued until nowadays, and terracing of the MU-2 top (terrace T2).

borderland. This study supports that the transformation of cut-and-fill landscapes dominated by incised stream channels with highly variable discharge commonly reflects the variable character, rate, and extent of human landscape modification in semiarid, poorly resilient settings (Brierley and Fryirs, 1999; Simon and Rinaldi, 2006).

6.3. Recent Yeguas River channel adjustments

Changes in climate conditions affecting the magnitude and duration of floods in Yeguas Creek can be identified in daily and annual rainfall

depth series dating back to the first systematic records in the 1950s. Although channel incision has progressed since the 1950s, it has been driven by long-duration rainfall floods lasting more than one week and with higher recurrence than recent floods (e.g., the 2018 flood event). In Yeguas Creek, we arrive at a conclusion similar to that for other basins in southern Spain: short-duration floods have become more frequent and severe, and they modulate the fluvial architecture in this semi-arid region (Bohorquez and Del Moral-Erencia, 2017; Moral-Erencia et al., 2020).

7. Conclusions

The reconstruction of the ancient-to-recent hydrologic and geomorphologic evolution of Yeguas Creek supports the conclusion that river degradation (i.e., channel incision) has been the dominant process in the alluvial plains of the southern Iberian Peninsula over the last two millennia.

Over the last 80 years, channel incision in Yeguas Creek has been evidenced by upstream-migrating knickpoints along the lower reach, where hydraulic jumps occur during floods with discharges up to 200 m³/s. The deepening and upstream migration of channel incision are exacerbated by changes in floodplain and water-use practices (e.g., destruction and abandonment of watermills, replacement of natural riparian forest with olive groves) and by riverbank stabilization (e.g., concrete channelization along the urban reach).

Two archaeological and radiocarbon-dated morphosedimentary units (Roman Period and 1200–1400 CE) and cohesive-bank terracing in the Yeguas Creek reveal that, following a period of river stability during the Roman Era, channel incision was the dominant stage for over two millennia, interrupted only by a short-term aggradational pulse during the Late Middle Ages. This Medieval unit is interpreted as an ancient aggradational knickpoint recording a period (Late Middle Ages) of floods characterized by high sediment discharge. High sediment discharge into Yeguas Creek and the consequent Medieval sedimentary legacy resulted from the combination of over 250 years of warfare-induced land disturbance (e.g., fires and forest clearance) along the frontier between two kingdoms (the Christian Kingdom of Castile and

Fig. 9. Map showing the territory of the Nasrid Kingdom or Emirate of Granada (dark green) and the mobile frontier territory (light green) between Castile and Nasrid Kingdoms during the 13th to 15th centuries in the South of Iberian (licensed under the Creative Commons source based on other maps from Harvey, 1992, and O'Callaghan, 2011, 2014). Look at the location of Casariche and Larva river terraces (yellow stars) just to the north of the mobile frontier regions downstream Antequera Plain and Guadiana Menor Valley, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the Muslim Kingdom of Granada), coupled with highly variable river discharge during the transition from the Medieval Climate Anomaly (MCA) to the Little Ice Age (LIA).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Fernando García-García: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Antonio García-Alix:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Patricio Bohórquez:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Blanca Pérez-García:** Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

G_Drive_Catena_GarciaGarciaetal_repository_2026 (Original data) ()

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